

IMPORTANCE OF FLORICULTURE INDUSTRY AND PROSPECTS FOR DEVELOPMENT OF FLORICULTURE IN UZBEKISTAN

Ismatullayev Jorabek Ismatullaevich

Samarkand agroinnovations and research university,

Faculty of "Economics and Management", 2nd stage bachelor's student

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13801971>

Annotation. This article talks about the importance of the floriculture industry in the world and the role of countries in it. The share and role of advanced European countries such as the Netherlands, Germany and France in the floriculture industry have been studied. In world trade relations, the production volume of countries was evaluated. It was considered that the governments of the Central Asian countries, including Uzbekistan, support producers in the development of the floriculture industry and that the ongoing reforms are in order.

Abstract. This article talks about the importance of the floriculture industry in the world and the role of countries in it. The share and role of advanced European countries such as the Netherlands, Germany, and France in the floriculture industry were studied. In world trade relations, the production volume of countries is calculated. The support of the Central Asian countries, including the government of Uzbekistan, to support producers in the development of the floriculture sector and consistent reforms were considered.

Keywords: Floriculture Industry, Floriculture Export, Floriculture Import, European Floriculture, Asian Floriculture, Government Decisions.

Enter. The global floriculture industry is moving from a traditional industry to a commercial one. The liberalization of the economy has encouraged entrepreneurs to set up export-oriented floriculture units in controlled climates. Considering the potential, this sector is generating income and employment opportunities, which will help to attract more women and increase the export volume. Floriculture is considered an important field of agriculture and has an important place in the economy of developed countries [1]. In advanced European countries, especially Germany, the Netherlands, Italy, France, the floriculture industry is well developed. For example, the Netherlands is the world leader in the cultivation of tulips, lilies, and hyacinth bulbs, while Germany specializes in the industrial cultivation of flowers such as roses, carnations, and lavender. European countries export flower products mainly to Switzerland, Russian Federation, Turkey, USA, Norway, China, Japan, Canada and others. Although the US produces the majority of floriculture plants and products, the country buys more from other countries and 19.5% of European exports go to the US. [2].

The spread and importance of floriculture in Asian countries are not inferior to European countries. The development and technology of floriculture in Asian countries is different from Western countries. It also focuses on the dynamics of trade flows and the seasonality of the flower trade. The original homeland of the rose, which is considered a plant of the northern hemisphere, is eastern Asia. According to reports, rose oil and water were first produced in Iran or India and then spread to Europe, North Africa and East Asia. The existence of the rose on earth has a history of at least 35 million years. The homeland of the rose reached other parts of the world from East Asia through trade routes. [3] In modern Asian countries, including Central Asia, we can see that the floriculture industry is growing at

a high level in recent years. We can see that the development of the industry has risen to a new level due to the reforms being carried out in Uzbekistan and Kazakhstan. [4] [5]

The development of floriculture is also progressing rapidly in Uzbekistan. In order to develop this industry, on the basis of the President's decision "On the further development of floriculture and horticulture in the territories of the Republic", the development of floriculture and horticulture in the territories of the Republic, the maintenance of local and foreign flower varieties, the art of floriculture among the population is a secret - measures are being taken to popularize the secrets, to further strengthen the export potential of agricultural products. In particular, the "Flower Growers Association" was established under the Ministry of Agriculture; A number of districts of the republic are in the process of specialization in flower growing. A large wholesale market of flowers and seedlings was established in Namangan, Samarkand regions and Tashkent city; [6]

European Floriculture Production Indicators:

It can be seen that the Netherlands, Italy, Germany, and France are in the top position in the statistics on the volume of flowers grown throughout the European Union in 2011-2021. (Graph 1) [2] [9]

Chart 1. The production volume of floriculture industry of the EU countries is in thousand pieces

Graph 1 shows that the volume of the Dutch floriculture industry has increased by 7% over the past 10 years. That's why the output of other European countries dropped sharply to -12.5%. During this period, France's output increased by nearly 20.2%.

World floriculture trade relations :

International trade relations are increasingly developing in the floriculture industry, as well as in other branches of agriculture. Along with developed countries, the demand for floriculture and flowers is increasing in developing countries as well. According to the Observatory of Economic Complexity (The Observatory of Economic Complexity), the largest exporting countries in the world are the Netherlands, Colombia, Ecuador, and Kenya; The largest importers include the USA, Germany, the Netherlands, and Great Britain. (Fig. 1) [10]

Exporters of Flowers (2018)
[Click to Select a Country]
Total: \$9.99B

Importers of Flowers (2018)
[Click to Select a Country]
Total: \$9.99B

Figure 1. World floriculture export and import statistics. 2018

The share of Uzbekistan in the world export of floriculture is \$72.3 thousand, and the share of imports among Asian countries is 0.26%. (Figure 2) [10]

Figure 2. The share of Asian countries in the volume of world floriculture export and import.

Figure 3 This map shows which countries export or import the most flowers.

Figure 3 shows that the volume of imports in the flower industry of Uzbekistan is \$2.14 million. The change in the value of foreign trade is -2.07 million \$. (Figure 3) [10]

Conclusion: Based on the studied literature and sources, it can be concluded that the floriculture industry is a rapidly growing and promising industry. We can estimate the share of countries in the floriculture industry through government decisions and the position of producers in international trade. Government support plays an important role in the development of this industry in Central Asian countries, including Uzbekistan.

References:

1. S. Directions, N. Trends, and F. Prospects, *The Global Floriculture Industry* . 2020. doi: 10.1201/9781003000723.
2. <https://www.floraldaily.com/article/9226524/4-12-billion-eur-of-losses-for-flowers-plants-sector-across-europe/>, "European Union 2011 – Statistics on the volume of flowers grown during 2021," <https://www.floraldaily.com/article/9226524/4-12-billion-eur-of-losses-for-flowers-plants-sector-across-europe/> , [Online]. Available: <https://www.floraldaily.com/article/9226524/4-12-billion-eur-of-losses-for-flowers-plants-sector-across-europe/>
3. 347-356 Wang, G. (2007). A STUDY ON THE HISTORY OF CHINESE ROSES FROM ANCIENT WORKS AND IMAGES. *Acta Hort.* 751, D. 10.17660/ActaHortic.2007.751.44, and <https://doi.org/10.17660/ActaHortic.2007.751.44>, "No Title".
4. <https://www.floraldaily.com/article/9480869/10th-anniversary-exhibition-flora-expo-2023-in-kazakhstan/>, "Kazakhstan Flowers Week 2022," <https://www.floraldaily.com/article/9480869/10th-anniversary-exhibition-flora-expo-2023-in-kazakhstan/> , vol. <https://www.floraldaily.com/article/9480869/10th-anniversary-exhibition-flora-expo-2023-in-kazakhstan/> , no. <https://www.floraldaily.com/article/9480869/10th-anniversary-exhibition-flora-expo-2023-in-kazakhstan/>

flora-expo-2023-in-kazakhstan/, p. <https://www.floraldaily.com/article/9480869/10th-a>.

5. "Flowers from the Netherlands are considered to develop in the climatic conditions of Uzbekistan and the types of fungi are identified," vol. 25, no. 4, 2021.
6. Ismoyilov, A. I., Rasulova, G. R., & Ergasheva, M. S. (2023). MANGOLD YUQORI AHAMIYATLI KAM TARQALGAN SABZAVOT EKINIDIR. *Academic research in educational sciences*, 4(SamTSAU Conference 1), 532-535.
7. O'G'Li, M. O. M., & Zayirovich, N. E. (2024). BAXMAL TUMANIDA OLMA YETISHTIRUVCHI TOMORQA XO 'JALIKLARI FAOLIYATIGA TA'SIR QILUVCHI OMILLAR TA'SIRINI IQTISODIY TAHLILI. *Science and innovation*, 3(Special Issue 20), 169-179.
8. Nortoshev, E. Z., Qudratov, B. T., & Rayimov, F. I. O. (2023). O 'ZBEKISTONDA BIOIQTISODIYOTNI RIVOJLANTIRISH YO 'LLARI VA "BIODEGRADABLE" DAN FOYDALANISH SAMARADORLIGI. *Academic research in educational sciences*, 4(SamTSAU Conference 1), 456-464.
9. Zayirovich, N. E., O'G'Li, M. O. M., & O'G, I. J. R. I. (2024). GULCHILIK MARKETINGIGA TA'SIR ETUVCHI OMILLAR TAHLILI HAMDA "FLOWER INFO MOCKUP" MA'LUMOTLAR MAKETINING AFZALLIK KO 'RSATGICHLARI. *Science and innovation*, 3(Special Issue 36), 461-467.
10. Яхяев, Э. Я. (2023). ҚИШЛОҚ ЖОЙЛАРДА ХИЗМАТ КЎРСАТИШ СОҲАСИНИ РИВОЖЛАНТИРИШ ЗАРУРАТИ ВА АҲОЛИ ТУРМУШ ДАРАЖАСИНИ ОШИРИШДАГИ ИЖТИМОЙ-ИҚТИСОДИЙ АҲАМИЯТИ. *Journal of marketing, business and management*, 2(3), 120-126.